

A TWO-PHASE ORTHOTROPIC MODEL FOR INTEGRATING RESIN FLOW AND STRESS DEVELOPMENT IN PROCESSING OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

An extension of the Integrated Flow-Stress (IFS) model previously developed by the authors for a composite material system with isotropic constituents is presented here for the case where the reinforcing constituents possess general orthotropic properties. The IFS model couples the classical model for flow through porous media used typically to simulate the behaviour of the composite during the early stages of processing when the resin is liquid to the classical solid mechanics formulation that describes the behaviour of the cured composite when the resin behaves as a solid. These two formulations are integrated into a single formulation where the transitions of the governing equations between these two distinct regimes of behaviour occur in a smooth and seamless fashion. The orthotropic extension of the conservation equations and constitutive formulations in the IFS model are presented briefly. Adopting a u - v - P finite element formulation, the governing equations have been implemented in a MATLAB[®] code and solved using an implicit solution method that considers both material and geometric nonlinearities. A case study is provided to show the capability of the developed computational framework for processing of composite materials and comparisons are made with the predicted results from the process simulation based on the stress model alone. The numerical case study demonstrates the significance of using the IFS model to capture the temporal and spatial variation of resin flow on the process outcome.

1 INTRODUCTION

An accurate predictive model that can capture the multi-physics behaviour of the composite structure as it undergoes the manufacturing process is highly desirable. The availability of such a virtual processing tool can reduce the risks and associated costs involved in the manufacturing of composites. However, development of such a computational tool is quite challenging because of the complex behaviour of composite materials and their constituents as a result of their diverse and evolving properties during processing.

Process modelling of polymeric composite materials is usually carried out using a sequential approach where different phenomena, such as resin flow and stress development, are simulated within different sub-models [1-3]. In this manner, the state of the material at the end of each module is used as the initial conditions for the subsequent step, thus neglecting the inherent coupling between flow and stress models as well as eliminating the cumbersome task of mapping the information from one computational code to another.

Recently, Niaki et al. [4] built on the work by Haghshenas [5,6] to develop a two-phase integrated flow-stress (2IFS) model to overcome the drawbacks of the decoupled, sequential approach. The integrated model formulation was developed for isotropic materials, which although limited in its applicability to certain class of composites, e.g. randomly distributed short fibre composites, or transverse plane of continuously reinforced unidirectional composites, enabled a seamless formulation that connected the two distinct behavioural regimes of resin flow and stress development. The conservation equations consisting of mass and momentum equations were presented and constitutive equations were developed for a composite system containing a fully liquid (unsolidified) matrix phase

that undergoes solidification during curing. Through introduction of a scalar state variable called solidification factor, the Biot's effective stress formulation was used to describe the early stage of processing when the resin behaves as a fluid. The formulation then transforms to a classical solid mechanics formulation at the other extreme when the resin is fully solidified (Figure 1). The predictive capability of the 2IFS-Isotropic model consisting of a highly compressible matrix phase (e.g. air) was also investigated.

The 2IFS-Isotropic model was then extended to a three-phase integrated flow-stress model (3IFS) by the authors [7] and its capability was demonstrated for process modeling of composite materials consisting of three distinct phases: a solidifying resin, fibres, and volatiles (e.g. gas/air as reaction by-products of processing). The predictive capability of the 3IFS model was shown for a debulking process at room temperature as well as curing of a three-phase composite material.

In the current paper, an extension of the 2IFS-Isotropic model [4] to the general case of orthotropic materials is presented thus extending the applicability of the model to a more general class of composite materials. The isotropic Biot's effective stress formulation is generalized for the condition when both the solid (fibres) and solid-skeleton (fibre-bed) possess orthotropic properties and the fluid phase solidifies during the process. A case study is presented to show capability of the 2IFS-Orthotropic model for processing of composite materials undergoing compaction and curing. The results are compared to predictions obtained from the decoupled stress model [3] which ignores resin flow and its interaction with stress development in processing of composite material.

2 INTEGRATION OF FLOW AND STRESS REGIMES

The composite system considered in this work and shown in Figure 1 consists of a compressible fluid phase (F) flowing through a porous medium (fibre-bed (fb)) referred to as the solid-skeleton (SK) made up of solid (fibre) material (S). The fluid phase solidifies during the process. For effective incorporation of all the diverse properties and behaviours of composite materials during processing into a unified model and accounting for a continuously hardening (solidifying) fluid phase, a new scalar quantity, λ , termed 'solidification factor' was introduced by Niaki et al. [4,7,8]. This parameter is a measure of the degree of solidification of the fluid phase and varies between zero and unity, $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$. The solidification factor could be a function of any state variable used in process modelling, such as degree of cure (χ), temperature (T), viscosity (μ), and even fibre-volume fraction and reinforcement architecture, depending on the type of material, type of process, and so forth. As shown schematically in Figure 1, the lower bound limit of $\lambda = 0$ corresponds to the unsolidified fluid. The fluid phase (resin or gas, as a special case of fluid), solid phase (fibres), and solid skeleton (fibre-bed) are incorporated into the model according to the Biot's poroelastic model [9,10]. At the upper bound limit of $\lambda = 1$ which corresponds to the fully solidified resin, there is no distinct solid or solid skeleton phases as the whole material is considered to be homogenized (smeared) into a continuum solid composite material. In the intermediate regime (when $0 < \lambda < 1$), the fluid phase is partially solidified and has a combination of fluid- and solid-like behaviour. While the material undergoes curing, the fluid phase/solid grains gradually contribute to the stress bearing part of the composite material (through contributing to the solid-skeleton). Therefore, the orthotropic mechanical properties of the solid/solid skeleton changes from the fibre/fibre-bed properties at one extreme to the fully homogenized composite material at the other extreme as a function of λ . In a generic functional form we can write:

$$\mathbf{D}_S = f(\mathbf{D}_f, \mathbf{D}_c, \lambda) , \mathbf{D}_{SK} = f'(\mathbf{D}_{fb}, \mathbf{D}_c, \lambda) , \alpha_{SK}^{th} = g(\alpha_{fb}^{th}, \alpha_c^{th}, \lambda) , \alpha_{SK}^{cs} = g'(\alpha_c^{cs}, \lambda) \quad (1)$$

where subscripts f , c and fb denote fibre, composite, and fibre-bed, respectively, \mathbf{D} is the material (constitutive) stiffness matrix, and α_{SK}^{th} and α_{SK}^{cs} are coefficients of thermal expansion/shrinkage and cure shrinkage, respectively.

Figure 1: Evolution of the properties of the solid/solid skeleton and fluid phases with increasing solidity of the fluid phase.

3 GOVERNING EQUATIONS

The equations governing the response of the system in the IFS model includes mass conservation of the system, momentum conservation of the matrix phase (assumed as Darcy's equation), and momentum conservation (equilibrium) of the system. It can be shown that for a composite system with a directional (orthotropic) reinforcing phase, these equations can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\nabla \mathbf{b})^T \dot{\mathbf{u}} + (\nabla \delta)^T \mathbf{v}_F + \dot{P}_F \left(\frac{\varphi_F}{K_F} + \delta^T \mathbf{D}_S^{-1} (\mathbf{b} - \varphi_F \delta) \right) - \varphi_F (1 - \lambda) \delta^T \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_F^f \\
 - (1 - \varphi_F) (1 - \lambda) \delta^T \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_S^f - \delta^T \mathbf{D}_S^{-1} \mathbf{D}_{SK} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{SK}^f = 0 \\
 (\nabla P_F) \delta + \mu_F \mathbf{S}^{-1} \mathbf{v}_F = \mathbf{0} \\
 \nabla \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{SK} - (\nabla P_F) \mathbf{b} = \mathbf{0}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where the subscripts F , S , and SK denote fluid (e.g. liquid or gas), solid (e.g. solid grains in soil mechanics or fibres in composite materials), solid skeleton (e.g. fibre-bed in this case), respectively. Also, \mathbf{u} is the displacement vector of the system (associated with the solid-skeleton), \mathbf{v} is the volume-averaged relative velocity vector of the fluid phase (i.e. flow velocity), P is the fluid pore pressure, μ is the fluid viscosity, \mathbf{S} is the permeability tensor of the solid-skeleton which is an average representation (or effective property) of the porous medium, and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{SK}$ is identical to the so-called effective stress of the skeleton. The superscript f is used to denote the free component of the strain, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, or strain rate, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$, and overdot denotes time derivative, φ is volume fraction, K is the bulk modulus, $\boldsymbol{\delta} = [1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]^T$ is the identity vector, and ∇ is the gradient operator defined as:

$$\nabla = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \\ 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} & 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

In Eq. (2), the Biot's coefficient \mathbf{b} represents deformability of the porous medium and determines the share of the pore pressure that contributes to the overall load carrying capacity. For the general case of orthotropic materials it can be shown that this quantity becomes a vector defined as:

$$\mathbf{b} = \boldsymbol{\delta} - \mathbf{D}_{SK} \mathbf{D}_S^{-1} \boldsymbol{\delta} \tag{4}$$

where each of its components take on a value between zero and unity. When the solid phase is isotropic, the general form of Biot's coefficient presented in Eq. (4) reduces to the typical scalar form of Biot's coefficient $0 \leq b \leq 1$ which is dependent on the bulk modulus of isotropic solid and solid-

skeleton and is widely used in both soil mechanics and composites processing [4,6-10]. The above equation is in agreement with the expression presented by Carroll [11] in index notation where homogeneous surface tractions were used to obtain effective stress law of the elastic porous structure. The rate of stress in the solid-skeleton is given by:

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{SK} = \mathbf{D}_{SK} \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_{SK}^{\sigma} + P_F \dot{\mathbf{b}} \quad (5)$$

where $\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_{SK}^{\sigma}$ is the mechanical strain rate of the skeleton. In contrast to the sequential sub-model approach, the proposed methodology, through the introduction of the second term on the right hand side that can be thought of as a residual stress contribution due to solidification of the resin, allows for the transfer of the pressure carried by the liquid resin to the solid composite material in a seamless fashion as shown in Eq. (5).

The governing differential equations of the system are converted into their weak form using the standard Galerkin method. The system displacement vector, \mathbf{u} , relative velocity vector of the fluid phase, \mathbf{v} , and fluid pore pressure, P , are discretized spatially within a low order bi-linear isoparametric element with 4 corner nodes for the system displacements and relative velocities of the fluid phase, $\bar{\mathbf{u}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{v}}$, respectively, as degrees of freedom and only one internal central node assigned to the fluid pressure \bar{P} (the so-called 4-1 element). An incremental form of a system of algebraic equations is obtained using the backward Euler scheme for temporal integration combined with the Newton's nonlinear solution method. The details of the iterative solution procedure and all the matrix and vector quantities can be found in [4,7].

5 CASE STUDY

As a numerical case study, we consider a unidirectional $[0^\circ]$ AS4/3501-6 CFRP laminate that conforms and is fully bonded to an L-shaped convex tool as shown in Figure 2. Only half of the laminate is modeled due to symmetry and three key points labelled A, B, and C corresponding to the corner, transition between the curved and flat part, and middle of the flat part, respectively, are considered for interrogation of numerical predictions. Top and side surfaces are assumed to be permeable and a 540 kPa load is applied on the top surface.

Figure 2: Geometry and boundary conditions of the convex-shaped angle laminate.

The laminate undergoes the temperature cycle shown in Figure 3 where the resulting viscosity and resin degree of cure are also presented. The cure kinetics and viscosity models for 3501-6 resin are adopted from Lee et al. [12] and Hubert et al. [2], respectively.

Figure 3: Time history of autoclave and part temperature and predicted resin viscosity, degree of cure and solidification factor.

The solidification factor, with its evolution during the process shown in Figure 3, is assumed to be a piece-wise linear function of the degree of cure as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &= 0 && \text{for } \chi < \chi_a \\ \lambda &= \frac{\chi - \chi_a}{\chi_b - \chi_a} && \text{for } \chi_a \leq \chi \leq \chi_b \\ \lambda &= 1 && \text{for } \chi_b < \chi \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where the demarcation points χ_a and χ_b are chosen to be 0.7 and 0.9 in this example. The solid and solid-skeleton properties are also assumed to be linearly dependent on the solidification factor as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} K_S &= K_f + (K_c - K_f)\lambda \\ K_{SK} &= K_{fb} + (K_c - K_{fb})\lambda \\ G_{SK} &= G_{fb} + (G_c - G_{fb})\lambda \\ \alpha_{SK}^{th} &= \alpha_{fb}^{th} + (\alpha_c^{th} - \alpha_{fb}^{th})\lambda \\ \alpha_{SK}^{cs} &= \alpha_c^{cs}\lambda \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The final predicted shape of the laminate is shown in Figure 4. Both corner thickening and lateral deformation at the edge expected for a $[0^\circ]$ laminate cured on a convex tool are clearly captured by the model. These two observed patterns in deformation, which are in agreement with the previous experimental observations [2], qualitatively confirm the accuracy of the developed IFS-Orthotropic model.

Figure 4: Predicted final deformed shape of the processed laminate shown in Figure 2 (deformations are scaled up by a factor of 2 for better illustration purposes).

The predicted normal (out of plane) displacement of key points A, B, and C as a function of time are presented in Figure 5 using both the IFS and decoupled stress models. It can be seen from this figure that full compaction is achieved almost 60 minutes into the process after which no significant deformation occurs in the laminate. The full compaction corresponds to the condition where the applied load is carried entirely by the fibre-bed with little or no pressure induced in the resin as a result of the prescribed permeable boundary condition. Also, the figure clearly shows the inaccurate stretching (positive normal deformation) of the points predicted by the stress model [3], which does not account for the effect of resin flow.

Figure 5: Normal displacement of critical points A, B, and C through the curing process

Capturing continuous change of resin/fibre volume fraction distribution is one of the advantages of the IFS model over the stress model since the stress model alone does not have the capability of computing the changes in volume fraction stemming from the flow of resin. Figure 6 shows the predicted distribution of fibre volume fraction at different instances of time. At the conclusion of the process, a uniform compaction within the flat part of the laminate is evident while less compaction is predicted at the corner due to lower fibre volume fraction in that region. These predicted outcomes and observations are in accordance with the expected compaction behaviour of $[0^\circ]$ laminate on a convex tool.

Figure 6: Fibre volume fraction, φ_f , distribution at different instances of time.

9 CONCLUSIONS

A methodology has been presented to integrate the simulation of resin flow and stress development into a unified modelling framework for processing of composite materials. The isotropic model developed previously by the authors [4,7,8], is extended to the general case in which the constituents can have orthotropic properties. The model presented here considers a two-phase system comprising of a solid-skeleton phase (fibre-bed) and a fluid phase (e.g. resin or air). Introducing a state variable to account for solidification of the fluid phase, the governing equations are developed for the case when the fluid phase (namely the resin phase) evolves during curing from an unsolidified fluid to a fully solid material. In this manner, the consistency of the governing equations is maintained with those used for each of the two extremes of processing: i) the fluid flow through porous media formulation applicable to early stages of processing when the fluid phase behaves as a liquid, and ii) the solid mechanics formulation that is used for solid composite material when the liquid phase is fully solidified. The FE equations have been implemented in a MATLAB[®] code developed in-house that use a backward Euler (implicit) time integration scheme combined with the Newton's iterative solution to account for both material and geometrical nonlinearities. The demonstrated capability of the new integrated flow-stress model in capturing the essence of the composite material behaviour during processing instils confidence in using the developed mechanistic framework to conduct process simulation of complex composite structures.

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